

Kinetics of Oxidation of Substituted Benzaldehydes by Pyridinium Fluorochromate in Acetic Acid – Perchloric Acid Medium

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Manuscript received 2 June 1992, revised 5 January 1993, accepted 19 February 1993

Very effective and interesting oxidising agent of chromium(vi), pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC) has been recently reported¹. It is being increasingly used as an oxidant for several classes of organic compounds. We report here the kinetic of oxidation of some substituted benzaldehydes in acetic acid–perchloric acid medium with this oxidant.

Results and Discussion

The rate coefficients are independent of the initial concentration of PFC, indicating that the reaction is first order in PFC. The rate of oxidation is increased on increasing the concentration of aldehyde (Table 1). The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{aldehyde}]$ is linear with a slope less than unity. The plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{aldehyde}]$ is linear and makes a positive intercept on *Y*-axis. This shows that Michaelis-Menten type kinetics is followed with respect to the aldehyde. The variation in the concentration of the aldehyde showed that the rate increases with increase in $[\text{aldehyde}]$, but the order is less than unity.

The rate of oxidation of aldehyde is affected considerably by changing solvent composition of acetic acid–water mixture. The rate of oxidation increases with increase in volume percentage of acetic acid. The rate of oxidation depends upon the polarity of the medium. When the polarity of the solvent is increased, the rate of oxidation is decreased. It indicates the presence of interaction between an ion and dipole². Similar phenomenon has been observed in the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by acid bromate³.

Reactions were carried out by changing the perchloric acid concentration in the reaction medium. Increase in $[\text{HClO}_4]$ was found to increase the rate of oxidation indicating that the oxidation of aldehyde is catalysed by acid. In presence of acid, PFC may be protonated. The protonated PFC may function as the effective oxidant species similar to the chromium trioxide oxidation,

The rate of forward reaction depends on the hydrogen ion concentration. As the hydrogen ion concentration is increased the rate of formation of protonated PFC may be increased, which results in acceleration in the rate of oxidation. At the same time, the rate of oxidation depends on the polarity of the medium also. When the polarity of the medium is increased the protonated PFC may be more solvated. The more solvated PFC may have sluggish nature towards oxidation. This may be the reason for the decrease in the rate of oxidation with the increase in polarity of the medium.

The rate of oxidation is decreased by the addition of electrolyte like sodium acetate, which may be due to the common ion effect. The common ion effect may decrease the hydrogen ion concentration, which in turn may decrease the rate of formation of protonated PFC.

The reaction does not induce polymerisation of

added acrylonitrile. This rules out the possibility of free radical mechanism.

The reaction is facilitated by electron-withdrawing substituents. The order of reactivity is 4-NO₂ > 3-NO₂ > 3-Cl > 4-Cl > H > 4-CH₃ > 4-OCH₃. The Hammett plot is linear ($r = 0.96$) with $\rho = +0.68$ at 308 K (Table 2). Similar phenomenon has been observed in the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by acid bromate ($\rho = +1.1$)³ and in the oxidation of aromatic acetals by chromic acid ($\rho = 0.4$)⁴. The positive ρ value indicates that electron-withdrawing group increases the rate of oxidation and the electron-donating group decreases the rate.

Experiments have been carried out at 308, 318, 328 and 338 K under identical concentration of reagents. Near-constancy in the values of ΔG^\ddagger for all the aldehydes shows that all of them undergo oxidation by the same mechanism.

The results suggest that the oxidation proceeds through an intermediate complex of the hydrated aldehyde and protonated PFC.

The above mechanism leads to the rate equation,

$$-\frac{d[\text{PFC}]}{dt} = \frac{KK_2[\text{PFC}][\text{aldehyde}]}{1 + K[\text{aldehyde}]}$$

Experimental

The substrates, namely, benzaldehyde and 4-OCH₃, 4-CH₃, 4-NO₂, 4-Cl, 3-NO₂ and 3-Cl benzaldehydes were either redistilled or recrystallised before use. PFC was prepared by standard method¹. Acetic acid (A.R.) was purified by the standard method. Conductivity water was used to prepare aqueous solutions.

Oxidation was followed at 420 nm using an Erma AE 11S photoelectric colorimeter. Oxidation reaction was studied only in concentration range of PFC where Beer's law is obeyed. The purity of PFC was checked by estimating Cr^{VI} iodometrically. A standard solution of PFC (0.01 M) was prepared in 100% acetic acid. All the runs were carried out under pseudo-first order condition keeping the

aldehyde concentration in excess over [PFC]. The rate constants were computed by the least-square method from the plot of log absorbance vs time in second ($r > 0.98$). All the experiments were carried out in duplicate and the results were reproducible with a deviation of $\pm 3\%$.

The product of oxidation of benzaldehyde by PFC was confirmed as benzoic acid by m.m.p., tlc and spectral analysis. The stoichiometry of the reaction [aldehyde] : [PFC] was found to be 3 : 2. Therefore the reaction may be written as

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION [PFC] = 1.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³, Solvent : HOAc : H₂O (7 : 3), Temp. = 308 K

$\times 10^2$ [Benzaldehyde] mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^4$ k_{obs} s ⁻¹
1.00	4.0
2.00	5.5
3.00	6.5
4.00	7.2
5.00	8.1

TABLE 2—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT (k_{obs}) FOR THE OXIDATION OF SUBSTITUTED BENZALDEHYDES BY PFC [Aldehyde] = 1.00×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [PFC] = 1.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³, Solvent : HOAc : H₂O (7 : 3), Temp. = 308 K

Substituent	σ	$\times 10^4$ k_{obs} s ⁻¹
H	0.0	4.0
4-OCH ₃	-0.27	1.8
4-CH ₃	-0.17	3.7
4-Cl	0.23	5.0
3-Cl	0.37	6.8
3-NO ₂	0.71	10.8
4-NO ₂	0.78	12.2

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